

BRESTA® Acoustic Gentle

Load-bearing ceiling element suited for high acoustic demand

The timber elements have integrated wood fibre boards for optimal sound absorption. Manufactured with a special CNC machine, the elements are assembled using glue-free wooden dowel connections.

Highlights of innovative features

- The elements meet the requirements of statics, room acoustics, sound insulation and fire protection in one product.
- In contrast to conventional acoustic ceilings with the same high performance, the sound absorption of this product is integrated into the static load-bearing element.
- Filigree optics enable a modern, contemporary architecture.
- The element can be further customized through inlay panels to increase fire safety levels or optimize room acoustics.

Improved indoor acoustics of buildings increase the quality-of-life in private, professional, public and educational spaces. They enhance attentiveness, performance, concentration and ability to learn. The product is leading example for high acoustic performance through constructive circular design in wood.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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